

Test Mode for FIR Filter Design Using FPGA

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Abstract--- This paper presents FPGA hardware implementation of circuit under test (CUT) in design for testability (DFT). A three-tap FIR filter is selected and implemented as a CUT using a low-cost test pattern generator (TPG). Full and partial scan design strategies are introduced in this paper. The full scan is proposed to achieve high fault detection efficiency considering minimum possible area overhead for the whole CUT at the same time. While the partial scan individually detects the fault in any part of the CUT. The proposed CUT architecture is implemented in VHDL and tested for area and timing optimization using various set of filter coefficients. Only 61 slices and 109 LUT from the available resources in Spartan 3 FPGA is used to implement the proposed system. The achieved error detection rate for the CUT is up to 100 % with a maximum speed of 479 MHz.

Keywords--- VLSI, FIR, ORA, DFT, TPG.

I. Introduction

The complexity of very large scale integration (VLSI) circuits design is rising [1]–[4]. This increases the demands of complicated and expensive Automatic Test Equipment (ATE) to test data and prolong the testing time. In order to alleviate these testing problems, new techniques are adopted in the industry to evaluate the response of the circuit within an acceptable cost [1,6]. Such techniques should ensure high fault coverage, low hardware overhead and short testing time [7], [8]. The high fault coverage is a very important task in integrated circuits testing. So, the Design-For-Testability (DFT) and automatic test pattern generation (ATPG) are used to increase it. Many techniques have been proposed to find some trade-off through these three aspects that are mutually antipodal [4],[5]. Testing techniques in VLSI circuits are very important to introduce quality in product functionality in both commercially and privately produced products [2], [11]–[13]. The affected areas of manufacturing, as well as the design, concerned owing to implementation testing on the circuit. Given this range of design sharing then how to go to achieve a high level of dependability in operation of IC is a base concern [14]. The DFT should be designed to attain a high-quality level that must be achieving low cost and time that included in this process. These two-design statuses are at always dispute. Both goals in consideration performance versus cost and time the DFT methods has become a major design consideration [15][16] [17].

One of the important technique that used in testing circuits is the ATE that relatively expensive. Subsequently, use of automatic test equipment in smaller applications become hinders. In addition, the enhanced level of integration ATEs became ineffective as there is an increase of testing time because it is inspecting the entire circuit [18]–[23]. Also, the development of VLSI the amount of volume confined in a small region has also increased considerably leading to an increase of test data volume [24]. Due to the advances in the embedded system on chip (SoC), systems cannot be accessed directly from out of the chip [3], [12], [20], [23], [25]–[29]. When integration density is increased the number of manufacturing faults is increased. Due to these issues, it becomes vital to develop a system that is capable to ensure valid test of new circuits. Thus, the idea of a new DFT the technique has been arisen, with which it became possible to generate patterns for self-test. It can be a test through maintenance and operation. The typical CUT testing architecture composed of four hardware modules: -

- The Test Pattern Generator (TPG).
- The Output Response Analyzer (ORA).
- Control Unit (CU).

- Data path Unit (DU).

The TPG is determined using a test strategy that performed by hardware testing overhead, fault coverage and testing time. The ORA analyses the test responses and test pattern to calculate trueness of the CUT. The CU is a central unit that controls all operations of the test pattern, test response and output result if with or without scan test. The DU is the circuit under test in DFT. This paper proposed a design for test DFT to improve its testability for FIR filter using the new technique. A three-tap Finite Impulse Response filters is used as CUT. The main feature of the new technique is to reduce the area of overhead and input test pattern. The fault coverage and area overhead are provided to illustrate the performance of the new technique. The rest of this paper is organized as follows: in section II, the related work is introduced. Fault model, test structure and Circuit under Test (CUT) are explained in sections III, IV and V, respectively. The results are introduced in section VII and the conclusions are listed in the last section.

II. Related Work

The FIR filter can be designed using RTL method includes Control and Datapath Units connected in the top level. Then, the modified whole flip-flop to scan is added to CUT and represented by the multiplexer, tristate buffer or exclusive OR gates. This design is flexible which it is suitable to select any flip-flop to be scanned during the set bit at the scan enable state [30]–[32]. The new test design used a full or partial scan methods to test any circuit, as shown in Figure 3. In the full scan design method, all flip-flops are replaced with scan flip-flops. The scan path of the full scan design method is a combinational circuit; design for testability can be applied to obtain high fault efficiency. For this reason, the automatic test pattern generation (ATPG) for a sequential circuit is difficult in general and not used [33]–[38]. Converting the sequential design into a scan design results. In other words, in partial scan method, the DFT can be performed for the portion of the circuit excluding the scan path [39]–[43]. However, a subset of storage elements is converted into scan cells and sequential [44]–[46]. In this paper, the two scan design strategies, and partial scan design are briefly introduced and a full scan is proposed in order to achieve high fault efficiency considering minimum possible area overhead.

III. Fault Model

The flowchart shown in Figure 1 provides the procedural description of the system as implemented using FPGA. The analysis begins with the specification of a new technique to select the CUT type and modify it to scan circuit. The flowchart show that the circuit is tested under normal condition (fault free). Then, fault is injected to the CUT using a specific control signals. Finally, simulation with characterization is done when detected a defect.

Figure 1: Flow Chart Procedural Description of Implementation CUT with Characterization

IV. Test Algorithm

The test of the CUT can be divided into the test of the sequential and the combinational circuit of the interconnections. Therefore, an overall test strategy in this paper can be summarized as follows:

1. First, the combinational circuits are tested with the interconnections using the proposed method in [47] that includes multiplier and adder circuit.
2. Second, the sequential circuit is tested using a proposed method in this paper.
3. Finally, the full-scan and partial-scan implementation is proposed in this paper which reduces the area overhead and it reduces the testing time.

Figure 2 presents the logic of TPG and ORA. The TPG is the test sequence in input while ORA is to check the output data when indicating a fault or fault free conditions. The flowchart of the algorithm, Figure 2, illustrates the state machine (ASM) for all states.

Moreover, it shows steps structure of the control unit that it determined from ASM for the new technique. At the beginning of the algorithm, it clears all the initial data registers. In addition, the ORA examines the CUT to check whether the CUT is fault or fault free. The fault is represented by Flag=1 while Flag 0 represents a fault free condition.

Figure 2: Behaviour Model of an Algorithm State Machine

V. Circuit Under Test (CUT)

Figure 3 shows the CUT block diagram. In this figure, the normal operation mode (fault free mode) is represented by feeding real input data to the circuit. While, the test mode (fault mode) is characterized by injecting fault to the circuit using Test Pattern Generator (TPG) or Scan Input (SIN).

The output of the CUT is the same as the test data if the input is TPG sequence, while it represents the actual output data in the case of real input data. The ORA performs a comparison between the output of the CUT and the input data to detect the defected results.

Figure 3: Structure of the Model Circuit

VI. Results and Discussion

The hardware design and simulation results are discussed in this section. The full scan design is implemented using VHDL code.

The Xilinx ISE V14.5 WebPack and ModelSim XE P.58f are used as synthesis and simulation tools. Spartan-3 xc3s50-5pq208 Xilinx FPGA boards are used as implementation hardware platforms [48]–[53]. The FIR filter is implemented using VHDL as a CUT for DFT. Figure 4 shows the RTL schematic view for the DFT circuit. The designed circuit consists of 8-bit Data input (DATAINWSC), three 8-bit coefficients (B0, B1, B2), 8-bit Scan input (SIN) and 16-bit fault input to the three AND gate and multiplexers. The system is controlled by eight signals. Three signals named as SE0, SE1 and SE2 are used to control the coefficient and scan input. The next three signals (SEA0, SEA1 and SEA2) are used to switch data input between scan and data input. One of the last two signals is used to load data to register (LB) and other (Fault_Set) is utilized to inter fault to the system.

Figure 4: RTL of DFT

In the simulation part, the designed system is tested under two modes; fault and fault-free. The state of without fault is represented by the first TPG which is done by feeding the three coefficient (B0, B1, B2) in parallel to the three registers, in a single clock cycle. An initial value of input data is entering to three serial shift registers using DATAINWSC port. This operation is controlled using six signals (SE0, SE1, SE2, SEA0, SEA1, and SEA2). The output of the three registers and three shift registers are fed to three multipliers and two adders to produce the output data after three clock cycles. The following five TPG test represent the faulty state of the CUT (fault-set 0): the first TPG is replacing data input that enters to the shift registers by scan input using the same filter coefficients. The second TPG is entering filter coefficients and scan input to the first shift register only. The third test is replacing the filter coefficients by scan input. The fourth test is entering full scan to register and shift registers. Finally, the fifth TPG is replacing coefficient value by scan input value in the first register and entering data input to shift register. The simulation results of the circuit designed under test is shown in Figure 5. The above procedure is named as fault set 0 test.

Figure 5: The TPG Simulation Results of the Fault Set 0

All these six TPG tests are repeated with fault set 1 (full fault CUT mode). The simulation results of this mode are shown in Figure 6. The abovementioned TPG tests scans the whole CUT for fault detection.

Figure 6: The Simulation Result of the TPG Test with Fault Set 1

The simulation results, illustrated in Table 1, show that the proposed system can operate at a maximum speed of 479.513 MHz. The minimum input arrival time before the clock is 2.586 ns, the maximum output required time after the clock is 14.024 ns and the maximum combinational path delay is 13.020 ns.

Further, the hardware utilization rate of the FIR for the CUT using Spartan-3 Xilinx FPGA boards is shown in Table 2. From this table, it is clear that the proposed system consumes a few hardware resources.

Table 1: Synthesis Results with the Spartan-3 FPGA Board

FPGA Board	Data	Slices	Max.freq. (MHz)	Throughput (Mbps)	Efficiency (Mbps/Slices)	Power (Watt)
Spartan-3	16-bit	61	479.51	2557.38	41.92	0.098

Table 2: Synthesis Results Using Spartan-3 FPGA Board

Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization rate
Number of Slice Flip Flops	48	1,536	3%
Number of 4 input LUTs	109	1,536	7%
Number of occupied Slices	61	768	7%
Total Number of 4 input LUTs	109	1,536	7%
Number of bonded IOBs	86	124	69%
Number of MULT18X18s	3	4	75%
Number of BUFGMUXs	1	8	12%

VII. Conclusions

According to the comparison of results of the simulation of fault-free and faulty circuits, it is proved that this system is 100 % capable to detect faults and give accurate results in high speed. The proposed design has the ability to detect faults inside the adder and multiplier blocks in addition to the circuits wires. The fault detection is done by using mask technique which includes adding OR gate to inject faults stuck at 1 and AND gate to inject faults stuck at 0.

Further, the FPGA hardware implementation of the proposed technique achieved a very high speed of up to 479 MHz with only 61 slices and 0.098W power consumption using Spartan3 Xilinx FPGA.

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